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ONEforest

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A Multi-Criteria Decision Support System For
A Common Forest Management to Strengthen Forest
Resilience, Harmonise Stakeholder Interests and
Ensure Sustainable Wood Flows

D7.2 Report on the dynamic value chain model

A Multi-Criteria Decision Support System for a Common Forest Management to Strengthen Forest Resilience, Harmonise Stakeholder Interests and Ensure Sustainable Wood Flows

Deliverable 7.2

Title: Report on the dynamic value chain model

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Executive summary

This document is the Deliverable 7.2

This deliverable aims to provide the development of the dynamic value chain model (DVCM) which is based on the specific material flows identified and quantified the system elements using Material Flow Analysis (MFA) along the Forest Wood Value Chain (FWVC), Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for each semi-finished product included in the FWVC in Europe and Social LCA. The DVCM will be applied to four Case Study Regions (CSRs) in Europe, namely CSR 1, Estonia; CSR 2, Grisons in Switzerland; CSR 3, Catalonia in Spain; and CSR 4, Hesse and Thuringia in Germany. The methodological approach used for DVCM was System Dynamics. The DVCM was structured in 4 sub-models that includes wood supply, wood value chain, economic impacts and socioeconomic impacts. These sub-models cover harvested wood in each CSR by 4 different forest management options, wood supply including forest operation specifically for each CSR in the 4 forest management options, wood processing up to semi-finished products in the different industries, considering the three sustainability dimensions: economic, environmental and social impacts. The outcome of the DVCM are the quantified indicators for the three sustainable dimensions as well (available in D7.3 Scientific dataset on quantified target indicators and the interlinkages between them).

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Glossary

CLD	Causal Loop Diagram
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CSR	Case Study Region
dmnl	dimensionless
DVCM	Dynamic Value Chain Model
EAB	External Advisory Board
FTE	Full Time Equivalent
FWVC	Forest Wood Value Chain
GHG	Greenhouse gases
MCDSS	Multi-Criteria Decision Support System
MFA	Material Flow Analysis
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
R&D	Research and development
SIA	Sustainable Impact Assessment
SD	System Dynamics
SFD	Stock and Flow Diagram
tbd	To be defined
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

Climate change and environmental degradation pose significant threats to the world, necessitating urgent mitigation actions. The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) aims to stabilize greenhouse gas (GHG) concentrations in the atmosphere to prevent dangerous interference with the climate system (United Nations, 1992). Mitigating GHG emissions requires both reducing carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions and increasing CO₂ storage (Machado et al., 2015). Forests and wood-based products play a crucial role in combatting climate change and environmental degradation (Ellison et al., 2011). Forests absorb CO₂ during their growth phase, while wood-based products store carbon for long periods during their use phase. Additionally, wood-based products can substitute non-renewable-based products, while forests provide essential ecosystem services and habitats for biodiversity (European Union: European Commission, 2019; Hetemäki et al., 2017).

To support the transition towards a circular bioeconomy and enhance understanding of the forest-wood value chain (FWVC), it is crucial to comprehensively study the entire FWVC, encompassing forest management, wood extraction, and wood processing. However, the FWVC is often examined in isolation, with limited consideration of its full value chain dynamics and sustainability dimensions (Auer and Rauch, 2021). ONEforest aims to address this gap by developing a dynamic value chain model (DVCM) that assesses the impact of the FWVC on regional development, considering economic, environmental, and social indicators. Furthermore, ONEforest will explore future scenarios to identify the impacts of changing climatic conditions on forestry, the economy, and society.

To achieve ONEforest overall objectives, the DVCM together with the Multi-Criteria Decision Support System (MCDSS) (see Figure 1) will contribute to development of guidelines for decision making based on, environmental, social, and economic indicators from different viewpoints. The environmental, social, and economic indicators gathered in work packages 1-6 (WP1-6) are merged at a strategic level in the DVCM by WP7, which results in the correlated target indicators. WP1-4 provides the harvested wood in four different management option, WP5 provides the forest operation methods and their impacts, and WP6 provides the interests of the stakeholders in relation to the target indicators through scenarios for future development of the FWVC. The effects of the selection of individual alternatives and their interaction on the FWVC will be investigated by WP7 and provided for WP8.

Figure 1. Conceptual visualization of ONEforest's output

The DVMC incorporates environmental, social and economic parameters, highlighting cause-and-effect relationships among actors and wood flow within the case study regions (CSRs) defined in ONEforest. The model will integrate material flow analysis (MFA), life cycle assessment (LCA), social life cycle assessment (S-LCA), and system dynamics (SD) to capture linear and nonlinear correlations, feedback loops, and time delays.

This report aims to provide the DVMC using sustainable impact assessment (SIA) methods, particularly focusing on MFA, LCA, S-LCA, and SD approach applied along the FWVC. Applying the System Dynamics approach, the DVMC is a discrete simulation model that quantifies the relevant system elements and the interlinkages between them. It covers wood supply, wood processing, and semi-finished products across different industries, while considering social demand, and supply factors. Based on the forest growth models and different scenarios for the future development of each CSR, the DVMC projects wood flows, value added and ecological and social impacts for a time period of 40 years. From this, information is provided to support decision-making for stakeholders in order to provide the impacts on the wood value chain and sustainable wood supply in the future based on different forest management options. .

1.1 Case study regions

Based in the MFA, system elements of the DVMC were defined and quantified. Therefore, the DVMC is prepared for every case study region (CSR) of the ONEforest project. The environmental and social impacts were assessed through streamlined LCA and SLCA, specific for each CSR and they were linked into the DVMC. The CSRs were chosen to consider regional differences in climate and forest conditions, forest growth and various wood supply chains. The CSRs were defined as: CSR 1, Estonia; CSR 2, Catalonia in Spain (ES); CSR 3, Grisons in Switzerland (CH); and CSR 4, Hessen and Thuringia in Germany (DE). Each CSR represents a specific type of forest in Europe, as well as, forest ownership, and wood industries available (see Table 1).

Table 1. Overview of case study regions.

	Estonia	Grisons (CH)	Catalonia (ES)	Hesse/Thuringia (DE)
Geography	Northern Europe	Central Europe	Southern Europe	Central Europe
Forest type	Boreal/Hemi-boreal forests	Alpine forests	Mediterranean forests	Continental forests
Total land CSR	4,533,900 ha	710,500 ha	281,000 ha	3,728,600 ha
Forest land	2,332,600 ha	201,240 ha	281,000 ha	1,443,300 ha
Managed forest land	2,003,800 ha	184,240 ha	187,000 ha*	1,356,700 ha*
Main species	Scots pine, Norway spruce, silver birch, alder and aspen	Spruce, larch and Scots pine	Scots pine and black pine	European beech, spruce and Scots pine
Forest ownership	Private and state	Private and state	Private and state	Private, corporate, and state
Wood-based industries	From sawmill to pulp and biorefinery	Only sawmill and energy production	Sawmill, poles and stake, veneer and plywood, wood energy products, and energy production	From sawmill to pulp and biorefinery

* partially protected

1.2 Report outline

This report first introduces the method and material applied to develop the DVCM. Starting with the SIA methodologies applied to define and quantify system elements, and the description of the SD method approach used to develop the model. This is followed by description of the methodological approach to the model value chain applied. Afterwards results are presented, the structure of the DVCM, the description of the sub-models that integrates the DVCM and the characterisation of the system elements of the DVCM. At the end of the report discussion, conclusions and outlook are presented. The outcome of the DVCM is presented in the deliverable D7.3 Scientific dataset on quantified target indicators and the interlinkages between them.

2 Method and material

2.1 Sustainable impact assessment

The definition of sustainable development was first described by the United Nations Brundtland Commission in 1987 as “meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.” In their definition, the Brundtland Commission presented sustainability as a two-fold concept encompassing both environmental and developmental considerations (Kumar et al., 2020).

Currently, sustainability is based on the concept of three dimensions which considers environmental, social and economic factors in the development. Therefore, sustainable impact assessment (SIA) can be defined as an integrated assessment that considers the three dimensions, ensuring a holistic analysis and its potential impacts (Tuomasjukka et al., 2017).

Based on the sustainability assessment tool framework developed by Ness et al. (2007), there are three categories of tools:

1. *Indicators and indexes tools* measure of most often quantifiable data that represent the state of economic, social and/or environmental development in a defined region based on historical data.
2. *Product related assessment tools* focus on flows in connection with production and consumption of goods and services. They assess of resources and impacts along the production chain or through the life cycle of a product.
3. *Integrated assessment tools* are used for supporting decisions related to a policy or a project in a specific region. They based on systems analysis approaches and integrating environmental, social and economic aspects.

The SIA tools used to develop the DVCM considered the three sustainability dimensions evaluating the past development (retrospective), and forward-looking future outcomes (prospective, forecasting) (see Figure 2). The combination of these tools also take into account regional perspective (MFA and SD approach), product perspective (LCA and SLCA), and they are used to support decisions related to policy (SD approach) (Ness et al., 2007).

Figure 2. Sustainability assessment tools used to develop the DVCM. Adapted from Ness et al. (2007)

2.2 System Dynamics

SD is a methodology used to understand the structure and dynamics of complex systems. This interdisciplinary modelling technique allows for the development of formal computer simulations for such complex systems, enabling the design of more efficient policies and organizations (Sterman, 2000).

SD, rooted in nonlinear dynamics theory and feedback control, offers a means to address practical challenges within cognitive and social psychology, economics, and other social sciences. This approach proves valuable in tackling complex, dynamic situations and overcoming obstacles to policy implementation. It is gaining popularity for devising effective strategies in both corporate and public policy contexts, and is particularly well-suited for modelling supply chains and designing policies (Sterman, 2000). The advantages and applications of SD are defined by Sterman (2000):

1. SD deals with the problems of modelling high-level, non-linear systems with complex feedback.
2. SD shows the relationship between internal and external factors in the model world.
3. SD sets the various control factors of the system and observes how the system behaves and reacts to trends.
4. SD models can be built at an abstract level with limited data.

This methodology became world known after the famous “The limits of growth”, the first report of the Club of Rome in 1972 by a MIT research team coordinated by Dennis and Donella Meadows (Colombo, 2001). Nowadays, there are multiple applications of SD, from corporate strategy to the dynamics of a disease or epidemic.

Currently, SD has been applied in combination with other methods in forest wood value chain to address the potential to support sustain both the wood industry and forest resource base (Jones et al., 2002), and to advocate joint between industry, university and government action in terms of research and skills development in modern wood primary industries (Baker et al., 2017).

2.2.1 Causal loop diagrams

The causal loop diagram (CLD) and its feedback loops form the basis of SD modelling and enable a qualitative analysis of the system. Relevant system elements, positive and negative feedback structure, causality and time lag effects for complex problems are identified (Sterman, 2000). The CLD permits users to define several key concepts, and it is possible to visualize the interrelationships among the different elements in the system (Sterman, 2000; Trappey et al., 2012) by including:

1. The system boundary, representing the primary variables of the system
2. The causal relationships and their directions among the system variables
3. The basic structure of the system, including the major feedback loop.

A causal loop diagram is composed of elements linked by arrows that represent the causal relationships between the variables. Variables are related by causal links shown by arrows, each causal link is given a polarity, that can be positive (+), or negative (-) to specify how the dependent variable changes when the independent variable changes (Sterman, 2000). The

relevant loops are emphasised by a loop identifier which allows to identify whether the loop is positive (reinforcing), or negative (balancing) feedback (Sterman, 2000).

A positive or reinforcing feedback loop is defined by continuous growth over time, indicating the divergence of the mathematical model. Conversely, a negative or balancing feedback loop in the system exhibits patterns of asymptotic growth or decline over time, representing the convergence of the model (Trappey et al., 2012).

Figure 3 illustrates two feedback loops. Within loop 1, the population's growth is positively influenced by the number of births, while the population's increase, in turn, leads to a higher number of births. In loop 2, the population size affects the number of deaths, with an increase in population correlating with a rise in deaths. Consequently, as the number of deaths increases, the population decreases (Kanti Bala et al., 2016).

Figure 3. Population causal feedback loop (Kanti Bala et al., 2016)

2.2.2 Stock and flow diagram

In the SD approach, the stock and flow diagram (SFD) illustrates the quantified modelling of a system. Stocks and flows, along with feedback, are the two central concepts of dynamic systems theory. Therefore, the SFD is a characteristic diagram in system dynamics. To do the transition from CLD to SFD it is needed to identify the stocks, flows and auxiliary variables of the system.

Stocks are accumulations that represent the state of a system at a certain point in time. Stocks contribute to the system's resistance to change and serve as a form of memory. By accumulating the disparity between the input and output of a process, stocks introduce delays (Sterman, 2000). The flows represent the rate of change in stocks. Inflows indicate input flow that adds to the stocks, while outflows signify the flow that subtracts from the stocks (Kanti Bala et al., 2016; Sterman, 2000).

Within the SFD, stocks are showed as rectangles, inflows are represented by arrows pointing towards the stocks to indicate addition, and outflows are shown as arrows pointing away from the stocks to indicate subtraction. Clouds symbolize the sources and sinks for the flows. A source represents a stock that originates externally to the model's boundaries, while sinks represent stocks where flows leave the model. It is assumed that sources and sinks have unlimited capacity and do not impose any constraints on the flows they facilitate (Sterman, 2000).

Figure 4 illustrates the SFD for a population. The births are the inflow and deaths are the outflow. The stock is the population which is determined by births and deaths. The auxiliary variables (birth rate and average lifetime) influence the inflow and outflow respectively. The blue arrow determine to which system element is influencing the auxiliary variable.

Figure 4. Population stock and flow diagram with diagramming notation. Adapted from Kanti Bala et al. (2016), and Sterman (2000)

2.3 Modelling and simulation approach of the industrial value chain

Industrial value chains are complex systems embedded in an economic, ecological and social environment. For effective modelling, it is therefore a prerequisite to understand the interrelationships and dynamics of the development and value creation of industrial sectors. At the same time, modelling can become too elaborately if all the relationships and causalities of the real system are considered without adding any or only minimal value to the model. Therefore, the real system must be abstracted and simplified for modelling without neglecting the relevant system elements, relationships and causalities. Therefore, the modelling procedure of the industrial value chain is based on an established, methodological approach to derive a simulation model (see Figure 5Figure 5).

* System Analysis: Description of the system elements and its interlinkages by applying system thinking and causal loop diagram

Figure 5: Methodological procedure for modelling systems (adapted from Koller and Berberich (1995) and Turner (2020))

First, the industrial value chain and its sector (real system) are analyzed. Basis for the system analysis is the MFA, LCA and sLCA, which was extended for the qualitative and quantitative modelling by a literature review, analysis of statistical and GIS data, company data and expert knowledge. This comprehensive system analysis provides the understanding of the relevant industrial sectors in terms of the structure and applied technology, the material and process flows and the corresponding economic, environmental and social elements. In order to consolidate the relevant system elements in terms of an abstract and simple modelling, while allowing a common modelling for all CSRs, the CLD method is used to qualitatively describe the industrial value chain and its sectors.

In view of the complexity of the industrial value chain and the transfer of the model to all CSRs, an abstraction and simplification is made for modelling the structure and technology as well as the value creation of each industrial sector. The latter is the core element of the industrial value chain model (here: DVCM). It is based on a so-called greenfield approach to model the value added, the technological and human capacities, production site and yield including the inbound logistics and other auxiliary processes of a plant. Result is a typical plant for each industrial sector that serves a blueprint and can be transferred to all CSRs.

This blueprint encompasses quantitative data on various aspects such as production volume, turnover, number of employees, productivity, capacity, number of shifts, number of apprentices, R&D activities, and incidents (both fatal and non-fatal accidents). Additionally, qualitative information related to certifications, social responsibility activities, equal opportunities, and other specific parameters are gathered.

This typical blueprint that represents an industry of typical size within the value chain, is also the basis for a bottom-up calculation of the value added. This imputed cost and revenue model is based on the investment costs (imputed fixed costs) and imputed variable costs. The variable costs are derived from an input-output model and be aligned with the inventory data of the LCA. Then, the value added is calculated on the basis of imputed fixed and variable costs and usual overhead rates for maintenance (investment costs only), administration and distribution as well as average returns in the sectors minus variable input costs (i.e., timber prices, energy prices).

For modelling purposes and similar to the LCA, both foreground and background systems were defined to reflect the CSR-specific aspects of the industrial value chain. The foreground system remained the same across all CSR, including investments, capacity, and number of employees. The background system, however, was adjusted to reflect the specific conditions of each case study region, including variable costs (i.e., transport distances, outbound logistic costs, energy costs, wages) and other relevant parameters.

3 Results

3.1 Structure of the DVCM

The DVCM used as basis the methodologies MFA, LCA, SLCA and SD to model the FWVC from forest production up to the production of wood semi-finished products linking the ecological, social, and economic effects. The DVCM provides information about the impact of the forest management on the regional downstream value chain. Figure 6 shows the structure of DVCM consisting in four sub-models: wood supply, production of wood semi-finished products, environmental impacts, and socio-economic impacts. The DVCM is aggregated as a one commonly SD model which will model the four CSRs individually.

Figure 6. DVCM structure with four sub-models

3.1.1 Wood supply sub-model

The wood supply sub-model considered includes the volume of the wood harvested based on the results presented in each forest growth simulation provided by each CSR (D1.3 Validated model for forest growth simulation of Boreal forests, D2.3 Scientific dataset of forest growth simulation of Alpine forests, D3.3 Validated model for forest growth simulation of Mediterranean forests, and D4.3 Validated model for forest growth simulation of Continental forests). The forest growth simulation considered four different forest management options: business as usual, intensified management intensity, extensified management intensity, and climate adapted forest management. These forest management options were adapted to each CSR conditions and characteristics. The dataset also provides the information of tree species to be able to classify the wood into softwood and hardwood, aligned to the different utilisation pathways in the FWVCs, used as a general MFA in the D7.1 MFA model and impact assessment through streamlined LCA/ S-LCA for each CSR.

The sub-model also considered the wood assortments, based on the results that will be presented in the D6.6 Wood assortment and quality forecast algorithm based on intended silvicultural management practices. These assortments are also aligned to the different utilisation pathways in the FWVCs, used as a general MFA in the D7.1 MFA model and impact assessment through streamlined LCA/ S-LCA for each CSR. The assortment used are sawlogs/veneer logs, pulpwood and fuelwood.

Additionally, the wood supply sub-model includes the results from the D5.1 Dataset of current forest operations impact WP7. The dataset will cover information from forest operations such as costs, productivity, GHG emissions, jobs. This dataset considers the tree species (softwood and hardwood), the CSR conditions and characteristics, and the harvesting technologies and machines.

In addition, the sub-model includes the wood flows of imports and exports, considering the past behaviour of these flows in each CSR, based on the MFA results (available in the D7.1 MFA model and impact assessment through streamlined LCA/ S-LCA for each CSR).

3.1.2 Wood value chain sub-model

The wood value chain sub-model considers the different wood-based industries were identified in the general MFA model, based on the different utilisation pathways in the FWVCs (results of MFA available in the D7.1 MFA model and impact assessment through streamlined LCA/ S-LCA for each CSR). The characterisation of each wood industry was done using the Modelling approach to simulate an industrial sector (see section 2.3 Modelling and simulation approach of the industrial value chain).

3.1.3 Environmental impacts sub-model

The environmental impacts sub-model considers the environmental impacts derived from the wood value chain sub-model per CSR. This sub-model uses the results from streamlined LCA as product-related assessment (results of MFA available in the D7.1 MFA model and impact assessment through streamlined LCA/ S-LCA for each CSR). Besides the environmental impacts from LCA, the environmental sub-model includes carbon sequestration in semi-finished products and its duration, substitution of non-renewable resources, energy consumption and post-consumer wood use.

3.1.4 Socio-economic impact sub-model

The socio-economic impact sub-model includes the socio-economic impacts from the product-related assessment tool the S-LCA for each CSR (results of S-LCA will be available in the upcoming update of the D7.1 MFA model and impact assessment through streamlined LCA/ S-LCA). The included impact categories were evaluated, considering if they applied to each CSRs conditions, if the category is quantifiable, and if it is data available.

3.2 CLD of the sub-models

The CLD of each sub-model is an overview of the DVCM, where the complex relationships are described in a simplified form. Each sub-model has its own system boundary to be able to identify:

1. Exogenous factor: input from outside the system borders. For example: key determinants from scenarios (T6.5 Future scenarios of the overriding FWVC), input from another WP.

2. Target indicators: output to outside the system borders

Figure 7 illustrates the diagramming notation. The arrows represent a causal link between the system elements, if the arrow is dotted that indicates that the system element belongs from another sub-model. As explained in section 2.2.1 Causal loop diagrams, to each causal link (arrow) it is assigned a polarity, positive (+) or negative (-).

Figure 7. CLD diagramming notation for the DVCM sub-models

The sub-indexes used in the CLD for each model are as follow:

- i: process chain
- j: tree species
- k: wood assortments
- l: forest management options
- c: environmental impact category

3.2.1 Wood supply sub-model

The CLD of the wood supply sub-model is shown in Figure 8. Based on the system boundaries, the exogenous factors are forest management option, wood price, and market development of wood-based products which is coming from the wood supply chain sub-model. The target indicators of the sub-model are harvesting emissions, wood regional supply rate, and competition between utilisation pathways.

The amount of harvest wood is mainly affected by the type of forest management option and the harvesting productivity. However, the harvested wood influences the number of employees in the forest operations, the harvesting costs, and the regional wood supply by assortment. The causal links between these system elements is positive, which means higher amount of harvested wood it will be need a greater number of employees, higher harvesting costs and more regional wood supply will be available. Or in case of lower amount of harvested wood, the number of employees, the harvesting costs and the regional wood supply will be lower.

The harvesting productivity, harvesting costs, accidents at workplace (forest operations) and the harvesting emissions depend on the harvesting technologies and machines. The harvesting technologies and machines depends on each CSR conditions and characterises considered in the input dataset from D5.1 Dataset of current forest operations impact for WP7.

The valued added of the harvested wood depends on the harvesting prices and the wood prices which is considered as exogenous factor.

The regional wood supply rate by assortment depends on the harvested wood and the wood assortments (dataset coming from D6.6 Wood assortment and quality forecast algorithm based on intended silvicultural management practices). And it influences the wood regional supply rate and the wood supplied on the market.

Figure 8. CLD of wood supply sub-model

The wood distributed to each value chain depends on wood supply on the market, imported wood by assortment, and the market development of wood-based products. And it will determine the target indicator of competition between utilisation pathways. The wood distributed to each value chain is a system element that influences the wood value chain sub-model.

3.2.2 Wood value chain sub-model

Figure 9 illustrates the CLD of the wood value chain sub-model. The sub-index i denote each wood industry (sector) identified in the different utilization pathways of the FWVCs, used for the general MFA model. The future development of the FWVC in each CSR will be integrated in the simulation of the DVCM and it will come from the scenarios developed with different stakeholders along the FWVC in the four CSRs (using the results of the D6.5 Narrative describing future scenarios of the overriding FWVC).

The wood value chain sub-model shows illustrates in general a wood industry. However, each wood industry will be simulated individually. The core of the sub-model is the production volume, applied technology and its capacity in value chain i . Depending on the type of industry, the volume is influenced by the relation main product to by-product, which is affected by the competition of utilisation pathways. For example, a sawmill industry might shift their relation main product to by-product if it is more competitive to produce a higher volume of by-products. However, the change is not immediately observed, therefore the influence between relation main product by-product and production volume in value chain i has a time delay.

The feedback loop identified are:

1. Investment/divestment in existing value chain $i \rightarrow (+)$ installed production capacity $i \rightarrow (-)$ investment/divestment in existing value chain i

This balancing feedback loop represents a self-regulating mechanism within the value chain i . When investment and divestment in the existing value chain increase, it leads to a corresponding rise in the installed production capacity. As the capacity grows, a company may become cautious about further investments to avoid overcapacity, which can result in a reduction of future investment and divestment. Conversely, if the production capacity decreases due to divestment or other factors, it could prompt a company to consider additional investments to optimize production efficiency. This balancing loop helps maintain a stable relationship between investment decisions and installed production capacity, enabling the value chain to adjust appropriately based on the interaction with the other system elements.

2. Installed production capacity $i \rightarrow (+)$ shift $i \rightarrow (+)$ installed production capacity i

This positive feedback loop create a reinforcing loop within the value chain i . When the installed production capacity is high, it allows for more shifts to be scheduled, which maximizes the use of available capacity and increases production output.

3. Wood distributed to value chain $i \rightarrow (+)$ production volume in value chain $i \rightarrow (-)$ wood distributed to value chain i

The balancing feedback loop involving wood distributed to value chain i and production volume in value chain i forms a self-regulating mechanism within the value chain i . As the wood is distributed to value chain i and enters the production process, it contributes positively to the production volume in that specific value chain. However, as the production volume increases, it leads to a decrease in the available wood distributed to value chain i , creating a negative effect on the input. This reduction in available wood may result in a subsequent decrease in production volume, completing the loop. The balancing feedback loop ensures that as

production volume rises, it eventually stabilizes by limiting the availability of wood, and vice versa, maintaining a dynamic equilibrium between wood distribution and production volume within the value chain.

4. Production volume in value chain $i \rightarrow (+)$ relation main product to by-product $i \rightarrow (-)$ production volume in value chain i

The balancing feedback loop involving production volume in value chain i and the relation main product to by-product i creates a self-regulating mechanism within value chain i . As the production volume in value chain i increases, it positively influences the relationship between the main product and by-product i , potentially leading to higher utilization or efficiency in the utilization of by-products. However, this positive impact on the relationship results in a decrease in production volume in value chain i , as resources are diverted or optimized towards the by-product i . This reduction in production volume helps maintain a balance in the value chain, preventing overproduction of the main product and ensuring a sustainable utilization of by-products. Thus, the balancing feedback loop contributes to stabilizing production volume while optimizing the value chain's resource usage and enhancing the overall efficiency and sustainability of the system.

5. Production volume in value chain $i \rightarrow (+)$ stock semifinished products i on site $\rightarrow (-)$ installed production capacity $i \rightarrow (+)$ wood distributed to value chain $i \rightarrow (+)$ production volume in value chain i

The balancing feedback loop involving production volume in value chain i , stock of semifinished products i on site, installed production capacity i , and wood distributed to value chain i creates a self-regulating mechanism within value chain i . As the production volume in value chain i increases, it leads to a rise in the stock of semifinished products i on site, as more products are being processed and stored. However, this positive relationship triggers a reduction in installed production capacity i , as the existing capacity becomes occupied with the growing stock of semifinished products. As a result, the decrease in installed production capacity i leads to an increase in wood distributed to value chain i to meet the demand for production. This, in turn, contributes to raising the production volume in value chain i . The loop continues to maintain a balance as increased production volume drives the stock of semifinished products, which in turn regulates the installed production capacity and wood distribution, ensuring a stable and efficient operation of value chain i .

This sub-model interacts with the wood supply sub-model to get the wood distributed to value chain i , the environmental impacts sub-model to provide the production volume in value chain i and obtain the total environmental impact of semi-finished products, the socio-economic impacts sub-model to get number of employees and shifts.

3.2.3 Environmental impacts sub-model

Figure 10 illustrates the CLD of the environmental impacts of the FWVC. Similar to the LCA modelling (D7.1), the system within the CLD differentiates between background and foreground system. Elements in the background system vary by CSR, the foreground system uses the same data for each CSR. Elements in bold letters are target indicators.

Figure 10. CLD of environmental impacts sub-model

The environmental impacts throughout the wood value chain consist of three main parts. First, consider the total environmental impact of semi-finished products based on the LCA results (available in D7.1 MFA model and impact assessment through streamlined LCA/ S-LCA). Second, evaluates the total carbon stock. Third, assess the total saved environmental impact of substituted products.

1. Total environmental impact of semi-finished products

The environmental impact of semi-finished products is related to the specific environmental impacts of transport of raw materials, steam production, heat production, electricity grid mix and fuel. These inputs are modelled using the cradle-to-gate approach and multiplied with the specific input per unit of semi-finished products. In addition, the specific environmental impact of production (gate-to-gate) per unit semi-finished product, auxiliaries (glue, adhesives and other inputs), post-consumer wood and water supply determines the environmental impact per unit semi-finished product. The environmental impact per unit of semi-finished product is directly dependent on the impact of its individual inputs. Production volume in value chain *i* and the environmental impact per unit of semi-finished product elevate the total environmental impact of semi-finished products in an industrial sector and in total across all sectors.

2. Carbon Stock

In relation to their wood content, wood products are able to store biogenic carbon that is sequestered during the growth of the forest (tree). This carbon stock increases with the specific carbon storage per semi-finished product and the production volume in value chain *i*. It is also augmented by the share of cascade use and the average lifetime of wood products, because the longer the lifetime of a product, the longer the carbon is stored in it. This also applies to use over several cascades. Otherwise, it decreases with rising amounts of post-consumer wood as the carbon is then no longer stored in the product.

3. Total saved environmental impact of substituted products

Wood products can replace various products and thus improve their environmental impacts. A so-called displacement factor determines the environmental impacts which can be saved by substituting one product with another one e.g., concrete with wood. On one hand, the total saved environmental impact of substituted products is directly influenced by the environmental impact reduction achieved per unit of substituted product. As the saved environmental impact per unit increases, the overall environmental benefits of substituting products also rise. On the other hand, another factor, namely the possible volume of substituted products, determines the total saved environmental impact. The higher the share of the production volume within value chain *i*, particularly for the main product, that is substituting another product, the higher are the total saved environmental impacts. By scaling up production in the specific value chain, the potential for greater environmental savings from substituted products can be realized.

The saved environmental impacts resulting from the use of substituted products and carbon stock are not offset against the total environmental impact of the produced semi-finished products, as this adjustment would distort the final result. However, it is essential to consider the effects of substitution and carbon storage in wood products in order to evaluate their comprehensive environmental impact.

The feedback loop identified is:

total volume of post-consumer wood \rightarrow (+) production volume in value chain $i \rightarrow$ (+) total volume of post-consumer wood

The total volume of post-consumer wood increases, possibly due to greater awareness of recycling, sustainable practices, or improved waste management systems, this increase in post-consumer wood availability feeds into a specific stage within the value chain where it is utilized as a raw material for further production. As the value chain uses more post-consumer wood, it may result in producing more products or materials that are made from recycled wood. This can lead to increased availability and use of products with recycled content. Consequently, the total volume of post-consumer wood continues to increase, as more products containing recycled wood reach the end of their life cycle and become post-consumer wood once again.

3.2.4 Socio-economic impacts sub-model

Figure 11 presents the CLD of the socio-economic impacts sub-model. This sub-model is based on the S-LCA results (available in upcoming updated version of the D7.1 MFA model and impact assessment through streamlined LCA/ S-LCA). It includes the social indicators from the S-LCA which were assessed along the FWVC. This sub-model interacts with the wood value chain, the environmental sub-model and the value-added model.

As market development grows, it leads to an increase in shifts, creating more job opportunities (potential of new jobs) and subsequently increasing the number of employees in the wood industry. This higher number of employees positively influences the overall production volume in the value chain. Moreover, as the production volume in the value chain increases, it leads to more total working hours and a rise in the number of employees. However, a higher number of employees may also result in an increase in workplace accidents.

Additionally, the growth in production volume positively impacts the market dominance of the wood industry, contributing to its economic development and further enhancing the production volume. Nevertheless, an increase in the production volume can lead to more workplace accidents, as well an increase in the production volume, may contribute to a higher environmental load.

Furthermore, as the total value added by the wood industry increases, it positively influences the industry's contribution to economic development, leading to higher salaries and promoting equal opportunities for employees. Additionally, an increase in the minimum wage results in a decrease in the gap between the minimum wage and what is perceived as a fair salary in the wood industry (fair salary i).

The feedback loop identified is:

potential of new jobs $i \rightarrow$ (+) number of employees $i \rightarrow$ (-) potential of new jobs i

As the potential of new jobs increases, it leads to a rise in the number of employees in the wood industry. However, as the number of employees increases, it can result in a reduction in the potential of new jobs. This occurs because as more people are employed in the industry, there might be fewer job openings available for new candidates, thus lowering the potential for additional job opportunities. On the other hand, if the number of employees decreases, it could potentially lead to a higher potential for new jobs, as there are more openings to be filled. This

balancing feedback loop helps to stabilize the relationship between the potential of new jobs and the number of employees, preventing the system from experiencing extreme fluctuations in workforce size.

Figure 11. CLD of socio-economic impacts sub-model

In general, the socio-economic impacts sub-model CLD highlights how changes in one variable can cascade through the system, affecting other variables and influencing the overall socio-economic outcomes of the wood industry.

3.2.5 Valued added model

The value-added model is included to examine the value-added characteristics of wood-based products and considering their production effect along the FWVC. The value-added model includes data collection using the method of modelling approach to simulate and industrial sector (see section 2.3).

Figure 12 illustrates the CLD of the value-added model. This model is based on the modelling and simulation approach of the industrial value chain. The CLD illustrates a complex system representing the value added of a wood value chain and its interconnections.

The wood price and raw material costs per unit are positively related, indicating that higher wood prices lead to increased raw material costs. The inflation rate positively impacts raw material costs per unit, as inflation causes overall prices to rise, the inflation rate also positively influences variable costs per unit, as inflation contributes to increased variable costs, and in addition, the inflation rate positively influences calculatory fixed costs per unit, contributing to higher calculated fixed costs.

Wood quantity per unit positively influences raw material costs per unit, meaning that more wood utilized per unit leads to higher raw material costs. As well, an increase of other raw material costs per unit contribute to the increment of the overall raw material costs.

Raw material costs per unit positively affect the value added per wood fibre equivalent by-product, indicating that higher raw material costs result in increased value added for the by-product. As well, the raw material costs per unit positively influence variable costs per unit, indicating that variable costs are dependent on raw material prices. However, the raw material costs per unit negatively impact total value added per unit, indicating that higher raw material costs reduce the overall value added for each unit produced.

Energy from raw material input reduces the purchased energy per unit, meaning that energy derived from the raw material reduces the need to purchase additional energy. However, the used energy per unit has a positive relationship with purchased energy per unit, meaning that increased energy usage requires more purchased energy. In addition, the purchased energy and the energy price positively affects variable costs per unit, indicating that higher energy expenses lead to higher variable costs.

Variable costs per unit positively affect manufacturing costs per unit, meaning that higher variable costs result in increased manufacturing expenses. Outbound logistics, salaries and other variable costs positively influence variable costs per unit, contributing to overall variable costs for the value chain.

The total value added is calculated by deducting the material input costs from the total costs of value creation. Consequently, the price of wood, which varies depending on the chosen future scenario in the modelling, significantly influences the value added. A higher wood price corresponds to a lower value added. Other raw material costs are assumed to remain constant. To achieve comparability across industries, the value added per wood fibre equivalent is calculated, aided by product-specific conversion factors. In cases where the value added comprises both main and by-products (identified by production volume), differentiation is made for the value added per wood fibre equivalent for main and by-products.

* affected only by several industries

** Relevant in products where the bark is used for internal energy production

Figure 12. CLD of value-added model

The value-added model CLD emphasize how changes in one variable can cascade through the system, influencing other variables and ultimately affecting the overall outcomes of the wood value chain. The cost structure in the value-added component is adjusted for inflation and divided into fixed and variable costs. Variable costs encompass factors such as energy and outbound logistics, which have external cost implications. An example of an external cost factor is salaries related to the socio-economic impacts sub-model. The remaining cost items are consolidated under "other variable costs".

3.3 Characterization of the system elements

3.3.1 Blueprint of a typical industry

The development of a blueprint for a typical industry was essential to ensure a robust and reliable approach in modelling different wood value chains. The methodology resulted in data that serves as the foundation for simulating an industrial sector, which, in turn, contributes to DVCM.

In-depth analysis of the industrial sectors in the case study regions involved the collection and evaluation of qualitative and quantitative information. This information provided insights into representative and a typical production plant, including defined capacities that accurately represent each wood industry considered in the DVCM.

To streamline the modelling process, specific parameters such as typical process technology, production size, and other quantitative factors were selected. Moreover, qualitative details such as certification types and social responsibility activities were also incorporated.

The final step in blueprint creation involved designing a simplified layout of the entire plant, accurately representing all areas of the site to scale. It was assumed that the planned production site could be replicated in the same manner across all case study regions. The blueprint was then harmonized and validated in collaboration with industry experts to ensure accuracy and reliability. Importantly, the resulting blueprint was consistent across all case study regions and did not account for CSR-specific costs. This means that the data generated within the blueprint remains unchanged in subsequent modelling processes.

3.3.2 System elements for the simulation model

The identification of system elements and the causalities between them were performed based on the CLDs. For a simulation model, these CLDs must be transferred to the SFD by quantifying the system elements. Subsequently, a matrix was constructed to describe the characteristics of these system elements as equations. Each element was classified according to the three fundamental components of the SFD: stock, flow, and auxiliary variable. Moreover, the units of measurement for each system element were defined, along with the sources of data, abbreviations, equations, and specifications such as whether it is specific to a particular CSR or wood species (softwood or hardwood). Additionally, the matrix indicated whether an element is an exogenous factor or a target indicator. Besides, additional system elements of the simulation model have been defined to describe the wood value chain quantitatively.

Table 2 provide the detailed characterization of system elements for the wood supply, wood value chain, environmental and socio-economic impacts sub-models, and the value-added model.

The indexes used are:

i: process chain identified in the MFA:

1. sawmill
2. poles and stakes
3. veneer and plywood
4. particle board
5. OSB
6. MDF, HDF, LDF, and other fibreboards
7. chemical pulp (kraft/sulphate process)

8. chemical pulp (sulphite process)
9. thermomechanical pulp
10. pellet
11. briquette
12. biofuels (e.g.: charcoal)
13. energy (heat, power, fuel)

According to MFA results the use of post-consumer wood applies to $i=13$, however this might change for future scenarios dependent on each CSR. Additionally, by-products are used as input for $i=4, 6, 7, 10, 11, 13$ and, as output for $i=1-3$. But it might change for future scenarios depending on each CSR.

j: tree species, this differentiation applies to $i=1-3$

1. softwood
2. hardwood

k: wood assortments

1. sawlogs/ veneer logs
2. pulpwood
3. fuelwood

l: forest management options

1. BAU: Business as usual
2. HIGH: Intensified management intensity
3. LOW: Extensified management intensity
4. ClimAdapt: Climate-adapted forest management

c: environmental impact category

1. Global warming potential
2. Abiotic depletion potential
3. Abiotic depletion potential, fossil fuels
4. Particulate matter formation potential
5. Water depletion potential

n : products that are possible substituted

The following abbreviations were used in the table,

1. FTE: full time equivalent
2. dmnl: dimensionless, as unit for % or rates
3. tbd: to be defined, for further development in the simulation

This comprehensive matrix will serve as the basis for modelling the SFD within the respective software tool for simulation purposes. The equations included in the matrix will be incorporated into the simulation as functions or tables. The results of the simulation will be obtained in Task 7.3, which involves scenario simulations derived from strategic options for policy recommendations.

Table 2. System elements of the DVCM by sub-model

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Sub-model: WOOD SUPPLY													
forest management option l	FMO _l	yes	auxiliary variable	$FMO_l = f(l), l = 1, 2, 3, 4$	dmnl	yes	no	yes	yes	no	forest growth model WP1-4	wood supply	no
harvested wood j (t)	HW _j (t)	yes	flow	$HW_j(t) = W_{i,j}(t)$	m3(f)/year	yes	no	yes	no	no	forest growth model WP1-4	wood supply	no
total number of employees (forest operations)	TNEFO _{j,i} (t)	yes	stock	tbd	dmnl	yes	no	yes	no	yes	within simulation	wood supply	no
number of employees (forest operations)	NEFO (t)	no	flow	$NEFO(t) = sNEFO(t) * \sum HW_j(t)$	person (FTE)	yes	no	yes	no	no	within simulation	wood supply	socio-economic impacts
specific number of employees (forest operations)	SNEFO (t)	no	auxiliary variable	$SNEFO(t) = f(HTM(t), j); f(HTM(t), j) = \text{time series}$	person (FTE) / m3	yes	no	yes	no	no	forest operation data set WP5	wood supply	no
accidents at workplace (forest operations)	AWFO	yes	auxiliary variable	$AWFO = \text{dataset}, f(HTM) * \sum HW_j$	person	yes	no	no	no	no	forest operation data set WP5	wood supply	socio-economic impacts
harvesting productivity j,k (t)	HP _{j,k} (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	$HP_{j,k}(t) = \text{dataset}, f(HTM)$	m3(f)/pmh0	yes	no	yes	no	no	forest operation data set WP5	wood supply	no
harvesting technology and machines j	HTM _j	yes	auxiliary variable	$HTM_j = \text{dataset}, f(FMO_l)$	dmnl	yes	no	yes	no	no	forest operation data set WP5	wood supply	no
total harvesting emissions j (t)	THE _i (t)	no	stock	$THE_i(t) = \text{Integral}(HE_i(t))$	kg CO2eq	yes	no	yes	no	no	within simulation	wood supply	no
harvesting emissions j (t)	HE _j (t)	yes	flow	$HE_j(t) = SHE(t) * HW_j(t)$	kg CO2eq/year	yes	no	yes	no	yes	within simulation	wood supply	no

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Sub-model: WOOD SUPPLY													
specific harvesting emissions (HTM _j)	SHE (HTM _j)	no	auxiliary variable	f (HTM (t), FMOI) := constant	kg CO2eq/m3(f)	yes	no	yes	no	no	forest operation data set WP5	wood supply	no
harvesting costs j (t)	HC _j (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	HC _j (t) = dataset, f(HTM, FMO _j) * HW _j	€	yes	no	yes	no	no	forest operation data set WP5	wood supply	no
specific harvesting costs (HTM _j)	SHC (HTM _j)	no	auxiliary variable	constant	€/m3(f)	yes	no	yes	no	no	forest operation data set WP5	wood supply	no
value-added (harvested wood) j,k (t)	VAHW _{j,k} (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	VAHW _{j,k} (t) = WP _{j,k} (t) - SHC _j	€/m3(f)	yes	no	yes	no	no	forest operation data set WP5	wood supply	no
wood price j,k (t)	WP _{j,k} (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	WP _{j,k} (t) = dataset (time series)	€/m3(f)	yes	no	yes	yes	no	indicators from WP1-4	wood supply	no
wood assortment j,k (t)	WA _{j,k} (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	WA _{j,k} (t) = dataset, f (HW _j (t))	dmnl	yes	no	yes	no	no	wood assortment and quality forecast algorithm WP6	wood supply	no
regional wood supply by assortment j,k (t)	RWS _{j,k} (t)	yes	flow	RWS _{j,k} (t) = HW _j (t) * WA _{j,k} (t)	m3(f)/year	yes	no	yes	no	no	within simulation	wood supply	no
wood regional supply rate j,k (t)	WRSR _{j,k} (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	WRSR _{j,k} (t) = RWS _{j,k} (t) / WSM _{j,k} (t)	dmnl	yes	no	yes	no	yes	within simulation	wood supply	no
wood supplied on the market j,k (t)	WSM _{j,k} (t)	yes	flow	WSM _{j,k} (t) = WSA (t) - EWA (t)	m3(f)/year	yes	no	yes	no	no	within simulation	wood supply	no
wood stock by assortment j,k (t)	WSA _{j,k} (t)	yes	stock	WSA _{j,k} (t) = Integral (WSA ₀ + RWS _{j,k} (t) - WDVC _{i,j,k} (t))	m3(f)/year	yes	no	yes	no	no	within simulation	wood supply	no
exported wood by assortment j,k (t)	EWA _{j,k} (t)	yes	flow	tbd	m3(f)/year	yes	no	yes	no	no	MFA results per CSR	wood supply	no

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Sub-model: WOOD SUPPLY													
wood distributed to value chain i,j,k (t)	WDVC _{i,j,k} (t)	yes	flow	$WDVC_{i,j,k}(t) = (WSM_{i,j,k}(t) + IWA_{j,k}(t)) * MDWP_i(t)$	m3(f)/year	yes	no	yes	no	no	within simulation	wood supply	wood value chain
imported wood by assortment j,k (t)	IWA _{j,k} (t)	yes	flow	$IWA_{j,k}(t) = \text{if } WDVC_{i,j,k} > WSM_{j,k} \text{ then } = WDVC_{i,j,k} - WSM_{j,k} \text{ else } = 0$	m3(f)/year	yes	no	yes	no	no	MFA results per CSR	wood supply	no
market development of wood based products i (t)	MDWP _i (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	times series (tdb)	dmnl	yes	no	yes	yes	no	future scenarios	wood value chain	wood supply
competition between utilisation pathways (t)	CBUP (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	tbd	dmnl	yes	no	yes	no	yes	within simulation	wood supply	wood value chain
wood (t)	W _{ij} (t)	no	auxiliary variable	times series	m3(f)/year	yes	no	no	yes	no	forest growth model WP1-4	wood supply	no
Sub-model: WOOD VALUE CHAIN													
production volume in value chain i (t)	PVVC _i (t)	yes	flow	$PVVC_i(t) = WDVC_{i,j,k}(t) * Pli_j * RPBP_{ij} * (1 + MDWP_i)$ AND $PVVC_i \leq IPC_{ij}$	m3(f)/year	yes	yes	yes	no	no	MFA results per CSR	wood value chain	value added, environmental impacts, socio-economic impacts
product volume in value chain i by-product i (t)	PVBP _i (t)	yes	flow	$PVBP_i(t) = PVVC_i(t) * RPBP_{ij}$	m3(f)/year	yes	yes	yes	no	no	MFA results per CSR	wood value chain	value added
productivity i (t)	Pli (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	$Pli(t) = PVVC_i(t) / WDVC_{i,j,k}(t)$	dmnl	no	yes	yes	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	wood value chain	value added, environmental impacts, socio-economic impacts
technological production capacity i	TPC _i	yes	auxiliary variable	constant	m3(f)/hour	no	yes	yes	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	wood value chain	no

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Sub-model: WOOD VALUE CHAIN													
installed production capacity i (t)	IPC_i	yes	stock	$IPC_i(t) = \text{Integral}(IPC_i(t_0) + (TPC_i * WHS_i * NSP_i(t) * WDY_i) + Tli(t+\text{delay})); IPC_i(t_0) = \text{CSR-specific AND} = SNT_i(t)$	m3(f)	no	yes	yes	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	wood value chain	value added, environmental impacts, socio-economic impacts
working hours per shift i	WHS_i	no	auxiliary variable	constant	hours	no	yes	no	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	wood value chain	no
working days per year	WHY_i	no	auxiliary variable	constant	day	no	yes	no	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	wood value chain	no
number of shifts in production i (t)	$NSP_i(t)$	no	flow	$NSP_i(t) = \text{Round}(NSP_i(t_0) + MDWP_i(t) / (TPC_i * WHS_i * WHY_i));$ constraints: $\text{MIN}(NSP_i(t) = 1), \text{MAX}(NSP_i(t) = 5)$	dmnl	no	yes	no	no	no	within simulation	wood value chain	no
technology investment (divestment) in existing value chain i (t)	$Tli(t + \text{delay})$	yes	flow	tbd	€/year	no	yes	no	no	yes	modelling an industrial sector	wood value chain	value added, environmental impacts, socio-economic impacts
new and established technologies available i	$NSTA_i$	yes	auxiliary variable	$NSTA_i = \text{dataset}$	€	no	yes	yes	yes	no	modelling an industrial sector	wood value chain	value added, environmental impacts, socio-economic impacts
starting of new technology i (t)	$SNT_i(t)$	no	auxiliary variable	data from scenario	dmnl	yes	yes	no	yes	no	input of future scenarios	wood value chain	no
subsidies	SU	yes	auxiliary variable	$SU = \text{dataset}$	€	yes	no	no	yes	no	policy analysis	wood value chain	no
wood distributed to value chain i (t)	$WDVC_i(t)$	yes	flow	see sub-model wood supply	m3(f)/year	yes	no	yes	no	no	within simulation	wood supply	wood value chain, environmental impacts

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Sub-model: WOOD VALUE CHAIN													
volume of post-consumer wood to value chain i (t)	VPCWi (t)	yes	flow	see sub-model environmental impact	m3(f)/year	yes	yes	no	no	no	MFA results per CSR	wood value chain	environmental impacts
total volume of post-consumer wood i (t)	TVPCWi	yes	stock	see sub-model environmental impact	m3(f)	no	no	no	no	no	literature	environmental impacts	wood value chain
share of post-consumer wood per value chain i	SPCW _i	no	auxiliary variable	constant, time dependent	dmnl	yes	yes	no	yes	no	input of future scenarios	wood value chain	no
market development wood based products i (scenarios) (t)	MDWP _i (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	$MDWP_i(t) = MDWP_i(t_0) + MDWP_i(t-1) * \text{increase rate}(t)$	m3 (f) / year	yes	no	yes	yes	no	input of future scenarios	wood value chain	environmental impacts
total environmental impact c of semi-finished products i	TEB _{i,c}	yes	stock	see sub-model environmental impacts	specific unit of c	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	LCA dataset	environmental	wood value chain
salaries i	SL _i	yes	auxiliary variable	see sub-model socio-economic impacts	€	yes	yes	no	no	no	SLCA dataset	wood value chain	socio-economic impacts
stock of semifinished product i on site (t)	SSPi (t)	yes	stock	$SSP_i(t) = \text{Integral}(SSP_0(t) + IPC_i(t) - PVVC_i(t))$	m3(f)	no	yes	yes	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	wood value chain	no
shift i (t)	SHi (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	tbd	dmnl	no	yes	no	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	socio-economic impacts	wood value chain
working days per shift i	WD	yes	auxiliary variable	constant	hours/day	yes	no	no	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	socio-economic impacts	wood value chain
time delay for investment in value chain i	TDIV _i	yes	auxiliary variable	constant	year(s)	no	yes	yes	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	value added	wood value chain
relation main product to by-product i 8t)	RPBP _{ij} (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	$RPBP_{ij}(t) = (PVVC_{i(t)} / PVBP_i(t)) * f(CBUP)$	dmnl	yes	yes	yes	no	no	MFA results per CSR	wood value chain	value added
competition between utilisation pathways	CBUP	yes	auxiliary variable	tbd	dmnl	yes	no	yes	no	yes	wood utilization pathways	wood supply	wood value chain

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Sub-model: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT													
production volume in value chain i (t)	PVVC _i (t)	yes	flow	see sub-model wood value chain	m3(f)/year	yes	yes	yes	no	no	MFA results per CSR	wood value chain	value added, environmental impacts, socio-economic impacts
total stock of semi-finished products i (t)	TSSPi (t)	no	stock	$TSSPi(t) = \text{Integral}(VSPi(t_0) + VSPi(t)); VSPi(t_0) = 0$	m3(f)	no	yes	no	no	no	within simulation	environmental impacts	no
volume of semi-finished products i (t)	VSPi (t)		flow (input)	$VSPi(t) = PVVC_i(t) * (1 - \text{export rate } i(t))$	m3(f)	no	yes	no	no	no	within simulation	environmental impacts	no
total volume of post-consumer wood i for material recycling (t)	TVPCW _i (t)	yes	stock	$TVPCW_i(t) = \text{Integral}((t=0 \text{ bis } t) VPCWWM_i) dt$	m3(f)	no	yes	no	no	no	within simulation	environmental impacts	wood value chain
total volume of post-consumer wood i for energy recovery (t)	TVPCW _i (t)	yes	stock	$TVPCW_i(t) = \text{Integral}((t=0 \text{ bis } t) VPCWWE_i) dt$	m3(f)	no	yes	no	no	no	within simulation	environmental impacts	no
volume of post-consumer waste wood i for material recycling per year (t)	VPSWWR _i (t)	no	flow (output)	$VPCWWR_i(t) = VSP_i(t - \text{ALSO}_i) * \text{SMR}(t)$	m3(f)	no	yes	no	no	no	within simulation	environmental impacts	no
volume of post-consumer waste wood i for energy recovery per year (t)	VPSWWE _i (t)	no	flow (output)	$VPCWWE_i(t) = VSP_i(t - \text{ALSO}_i) * \text{SEUPW}_i(t)$	m3(f)	no	yes	no	no	no	within simulation	environmental impacts	no
total environmental impact of semi-finished products i,c per year (t)	TEBY _{i,c}	no	flow	$TEBY_{i,c} = \text{EISPI}_{i,c} * PVVC_i(t)$	unit of specific c / (m3(f) / year)	yes	yes	no	no	yes	within simulation	environmental impacts	wood value chain
total environmental impact of semi-finished products i,c (t)	TEB _{i,c}	yes	stock	$TEB_{i,c} = \text{Integral}(t=0 \text{ bis } t) (\text{EISPI}_{i,c} * PVVC_i) dt$	specific unit of c	yes	yes	no	no	yes	within simulation	environmental impacts	wood value chain

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Sub-model: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT													
specific environmental impact of auxiliaries (glue, adhesives and other inputs) c	SEIA _c	no	auxiliary variable	constant	specific unit of c /m3 or specific unit of c /kg	no	no	no	no	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
environmental impact of auxiliaries i,c (glue, adhesives and other inputs)	EIA _{i,c}	yes	auxiliary variable	$EIA_{i,c} = SEIA_c * SIASP_i$	specific unit of c /m3 or specific unit of c /kg	no	yes	no	no	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
specific input of auxiliaries (glue, adhesives and other inputs) per semi-finished product i	SIASP _i	no	auxiliary variable	constant	kg/kg or kg/m3	no	yes	no	no	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
environmental impact of raw material transport i,c (cradle-to-gate)	EIRMT _{i,c}	yes	auxiliary variable	$EIRMT_{i,c} = WSM_{j,k}(t) * SEIT_c * ATD_i$ (cradle-to-gate)	specific unit of c /m3 or specific unit of c /kg	yes	yes	no	yes	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
average transport distance of wood i (cradle-to-gate)	ATD _i	no	auxiliary variable	CSR-specific constant	km	yes	no	no	no	no	MFA results per CSR	environmental impacts	no
specific environmental impact of transport c (cradle-to-gate)	SEIT _c	no	auxiliary variable	constant	c/tkm	no	no	no	yes	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
wood supplied on the market (t)	WSM _{j,k}(t)}	no	auxiliary variable	see sub-model wood supply	t m3	yes	no	yes	no	no	MFA results per CSR	wood value chain	no

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Sub-model: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT													
specific environmental impact of water supply c (cradle-to-gate)	$SEIWS_c$	no	auxiliary variable	constant	specific unit of c /m ³ specific unit of c /kg	no	no	no	yes	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
environmental impact of water supply i,c (cradle-to-gate)	$EIWS_{i,c}$	yes	auxiliary variable	$EIWS_{i,c} = SEIWS_c$ (cradle-to-gate) * $SIWSP_i$	specific unit of c /m ³ specific unit of c /kg	no	yes	no	yes	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
specific input of water per semi-finished product i	$SIWSP_i$	no	auxiliary variable	constant	l/kg l/m ³	no	yes	no	no	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
specific environmental impact of steam production c (cradle-to-gate)	$SEISP_c$	no	auxiliary variable	CSR-specific constant	specific unit of c /MJ	yes	no	no	yes	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
environmental impact of steam production i,c (cradle-to-gate)	$EISTP_{i,c}$	yes	auxiliary variable	$EISTP_{i,c} = SEISP_c$ (cradle-to-gate) * $SISP_c$	specific unit of c /m ³ specific unit of c /kg	yes	yes	no	yes	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
specific input of steam per semi-finished product i	$SISP_i$	no	auxiliary variable	constant	MJ/kg MJ/m ³	no	yes	no	no	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
specific environmental impact of heat production c (cradle-to-gate)	$SEIHP_c$	no	auxiliary variable	constant	specific unit of c /MJ	yes	no	no	yes	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Sub-model: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT													
environmental impact of heat production i,c (cradle-to-gate)	EIHP _{i,c}	yes	auxiliary variable	$EIHP_{i,c} = SEIHP_c \text{ (cradle-to-gate)} * SIHSP_i$	specific unit of c /m3 specific unit of c /kg	yes	yes	no	yes	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
specific input of heat per semi-finished product i	SIHSP _i	no	auxiliary variable	constant	MJ/kg MJ/m3	no	yes	no	no	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
specific environmental impact of electricity grid mix c (cradle-to-gate)	SEIEG _c	no	auxiliary variable	time-dependent constant	specific unit of c /MJ	yes	no	no	yes	no	LCA dataset, literature	environmental impacts	no
environmental impact of electricity grid mix i,c (cradle-to-gate)	EIEG _{i,c}	yes	auxiliary variable	$EIEG_{i,c} = SEIEG_c \text{ (cradle-to-gate)} * SIEGSP_i$	specific unit of c /m3 specific unit of c /kg	yes	yes	no	yes	no	LCA dataset, literature	environmental impacts	no
specific input of electricity per semi-finished product i	SIEGSP _i	no	auxiliary variable	constant	MJ/kg MJ/m3	no	yes	no	no	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
specific environmental impact of fuel c (cradle-to-gate)	SEIF _c	no	auxiliary variable	constant	specific unit of c /MJ	yes	no	no	yes	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
environmental impact of fuel i,c (cradle-to-gate)	EIEGi,c	yes	auxiliary variable	$EIEG_{i,c} = SEIF_c \text{ (cradle-to-gate)} * SIFSP_i$	specific unit of c /m3 specific unit of c /kg	yes	yes	no	yes	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
specific input of fuel per semi-finished product i	SIFSP _i	no	auxiliary variable	constant	l/kg l/m3	no	yes	no	no	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Sub-model: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT													
specific environmental impact of production (gate-to-gate) per unit of semi-finished product i,c	SEIPSP _{i,c}	yes	auxiliary variable	$SEIPSP_{i,c} = SEIF_c (\text{gate-to-gate}) * SIFSP_i + SEIEG_c (\text{gate-to-gate}) * SIEGSP_i + SEIHP_c (\text{gate-to-gate}) * SIHSP_i + SEISP_c (\text{gate-to-gate}) * SISP_c + SEIT_c (\text{gate-to-gate}) * WSM_{j,k} * ATD_i (\text{cradle-to-gate}) + SEIWS_c (\text{gate-to-gate}) * SIWSP_i$	specific unit of c /m3 specific unit of c/kg	no	yes	no	no	no	LCA dataset	environmental impacts	no
environmental impact per unit of semi-finished product i,c (t)	EISP _{i,c} (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	$EISP_{i,c} (t) = EIRMT_{i,c} (\text{cradle-to-gate}) + EIWS_{i,c} (\text{cradle-to-gate}) + EIHP_{i,c} (\text{cradle-to-gate}) + EIEG_{i,c} (\text{cradle-to-gate}) + SEIPSP_{i,c} + EIA_{i,c}$	specific unit of c /m3 specific unit of c/kg	yes	yes	no	no	no	within simulation	environmental impacts	no
environmental impact per unit of substituted product i,c	EISUP _{i,c}	yes	auxiliary variable	$EISUP_{i,c} = (EIAP_{i,c} - EISUP_{i,c}) / (WUSP_i - WUA_i)$	specific unit of c /m3 specific unit of c/kg	no	yes	no	no	no	literature	environmental impacts	no
WU semi-finished product i	WUSP _i	no	auxiliary variable	constant	mass units of C	no	no	no	yes	no	literature	environmental impacts	no
WU alternative i	WUA _i	no	auxiliary variable	constant	mass units of C	no	no	no	yes	no	literature	environmental impacts	no
possible volume of substituted product i (t)	PVSUP _i (t)	no	auxiliary variable	time-dependant constant	t m3	no	yes	no	yes	no	literature	environmental impacts	no
environmental impact per unit of alternative product i,c	EIAP _{i,c}	no	auxiliary variable	constant	specific unit of c/m3 specific unit of c/kg	no	no	no	yes	no	literature	environmental impacts	no

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Sub-model: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT													
total saved environmental impact of substituted product i,c per year (t)	$TSEISUP_{i,c}(t)$	no	flow	$TSEISUP_{i,c}(t) = PVSUP_i(t) * EISUP_{i,c}$	specific unit of c / year	no	no	no	no	yes	within simulation	environmental impacts	no
total saved environmental impact of substituted product i,c (t)	$TSEISUP_{i,c}(t)$	yes	stock	$TSEISUP_{i,c}(t) = \text{integral}(t=0 \text{ bis } t) PVSUP_i * EISUP_{i,c} dt$	specific unit of c	no	no	no	no	yes	within simulation	environmental impacts	no
specific carbon storage per semi-finished product i	$SCSSP_i$	yes	auxiliary variable	constant	kg CO2 eq./m3 kg CO2 eq./kg	no	no	no	no	no	literature	environmental impacts	no
total carbon stock (t)	$TCS(t)$	yes	stock	$TCS = \text{integral}(t=0 \text{ bis } t) (VSP_i(t_0) + (VSP_i(t) - (VPSWWR_i(t) + VPSWWE_i(t)) * SCSSP_i) dt; VSP_i(t_0) = 0$	kg CO2 eq.	no	no	no	no	yes	within simulation	environmental impacts	no
increase of total carbon stock per year (t)	$ITCSY(t)$	no	flow	$ITCSY(t) = VSP_i(t) * SCSSP_i$	kg CO2 eq.	no	no	no	no	yes	within simulation	environmental impacts	no
decrease of total carbon stock per year (t)	$DTCSY(t)$	no	flow	$DTCSY(t) = ((VPCWWR_i(t) + VPCWWE_i(t)) * SCSSP_i)$	kg CO2 eq.	no	no	no	no	no	within simulation	environmental impacts	no
average lifetime of semi-finished product i	$ALSO_i$	yes	auxiliary variable	product specific constant (average, mean)	years per product m3	no	no	no	no	no	literature	environmental impacts	no
share of material recycling i	SMR_i	yes	auxiliary variable	$SMR_i = 1 - SEUPW_i$	dmnl	no	no	no	no	no	literature	environmental impacts	no
share of energetic use of post-consumer wood i	$SEUPW_i$	no	auxiliary variable	time-dependant constant	dmnl	no	yes	no	no	no	literature	environmental impacts	no
share of scraped semi-finished product i (t)	$SSSP_i(t)$	no	auxiliary variable	semi-finished product-specific constant	dmnl	no	yes	no	no	no	distribution curve of average life time	environmental impacts	no

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Sub-model: SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS													
market dominance (number of companies i)	MDNC _i (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	MDNC _i = IPC _i / PVVC _i	dmnl	yes	yes	yes	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	socio-economic impacts	no
installed production capacity i (t)	IPC _i	yes	stock	see sub-model wood value chain	m ³ (f)	no	yes	yes	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	wood value chain	value added, environmental impacts, socio-economic impacts
potential of new jobs i (t)	PNJ _i	yes	flow	PNJ _i = (SH _i * ESH _i) - NE _i	/year	yes	yes	no	no	no	SLCA dataset	socio-economic impacts	no
shift i (t)	SH _i	yes	auxiliary variable	SH _i = IF (MDWP _i * TPP / HPS) ≤ (NE _i / ESH _i), THEN (MDWP _i * TPP), ELSE (NE _i / ESH _i)	dmnl	no	no	no	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	socio-economic impacts	wood value chain
hours per shift	HPS	no	auxiliary variable	constant	h	no	no	no	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	socio-economic impacts	no
employees per shift	ESH _i (t)	no	auxiliary variable	tbd	dmnl	yes	no	no	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	socio-economic impacts	no
market development wood based products i (scenarios)	MDWPI (t)	yes	flow	see sub-model wood supply chain	m ³ /year	no	no	yes	yes	no	modelling an industrial sector	wood value chain	socio-economic impacts
production volume in value chain i	PVVC _i (t)	yes	flow	see sub-model wood value chain	m ³ (f)/year	yes	yes	yes	no	no	MFA results per CSR	wood value chain	value added, environmental impacts, socio-economic impacts
total working hours i per year (t)	TWH _i (t)	yes	stock	TWH _i (t) = Integral (t=0 bis t) (TWH _i (t ₀) + WH _i (t)) dt, THW _i (t ₀) = 0	h	no	yes	yes	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	socio-economic impacts	no

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Sub-model: SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS													
working hours i per year (t)	WH _i (t)	no	flow	WH _i (t) = PVVC _i (t)* (ESP _i (t))	h/year	no	yes	no	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	socio-economic impacts	no
employees per semi-finished product i (t)	ESP _i (t)	no	auxiliary variable	tbd	dmnl	no	yes	no	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	socio-economic impacts	no
total number of employees i (t)	TNE _i (t)	yes	stock	TNE _i (t) = Integral (t=0 bis t) (THE _i (t ₀) +	dmnl	no	yes	no	no	yes	within simulation	socio-economic impacts	no
increase of number of employees i (t)	INE _i (t)	no	flow	IF (TNE _i (t-1) <= 'NE _i (t); 'NE _i (t) - TNE _i (t-1); 0)	dmnl	yes	yes	no	no	yes	within simulation	socio-economic impacts	no
decrease of number of employees i (t)	DNE _i (t)	no	flow	IF (TNE _i (t-1) > 'NE _i (t); TNE _i (t-1) - 'NE _i (t); 0)	dmnl	yes	yes	no	no	yes	within simulation	socio-economic impacts	no
number of employees i (t)	NE _i (t)	no	auxiliary variable	NE _i (t) = WH _i (t) / (CWT _i *(WD / AWDW)	dmnl	yes	yes	no	no	yes	SLCA dataset	socio-economic impacts	no
working days per shift i	WD	yes	auxiliary variable	constant	days/year	yes	no	no	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	socio-economic impacts	wood value chain
average working days per week	AWDW	no	auxiliary variable	constant	days/week	yes	no	no	no	no	literature	socio-economic impacts	no
accidents at workplace i	AW _i	yes	flow	constant	#/1000 employees	yes	yes	no	no	yes	SLCA dataset	socio-economic impacts	no
contractual working time i	CWT _i	no	auxiliary variable	CSR specific constant	h/week	yes	yes		no	no	literature	socio-economic impacts	no
contribution to economic development i (t)	CED _i (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	CED _i (t) = PVVC _i (t) * TVA _{i,j,k} (t)	€/year	yes	yes	no	no	yes	SLCA dataset	wood value chain	socio-economic impacts
total value added per unit i,j,k (t)	TVAU _{i,j,k}	yes	auxiliary variable	see value added model	€/m3(f)	yes	yes	yes	no	no	within simulation	value added	socio-economic impacts
salaries i (t)	SL _i	yes	auxiliary variable	SL _i (t) = WG _i * WH _i (t)	€	yes	yes	no	no	no	SLCA dataset	wood value chain	socio-economic impacts

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Sub-model: SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS													
wage i (t)	WGi (t)	no	auxiliary variable	constant * IR (t)	€/h	yes	yes	no	yes	no	literature	socio-economic impacts	no
equal opportunities i	EO _i	yes	auxiliary variable	EO _i = SW /SM *100	dmnl	yes	yes	no	no	yes	SLCA dataset	socio-economic impacts	no
salary men	SM	no	auxiliary variable	constant	€	yes	yes	no	yes	no	literature	socio-economic impacts	no
salary women	SW	no	auxiliary variable	constant	€	yes	yes	no	yes	no	literature	socio-economic impacts	no
environmental load	EL	yes	auxiliary variable	constant	specific unit of c / year	no	no	no	yes	no	literature	socio-economic impacts	no
contribution to environmental load i (t)	CEL _i (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	CEL _i (t) = EISP _{i,c} * PVVC _i (t)/ EL *100	dmnl	yes	no	no	no	yes	LCA dataset	socio-economic impacts	no
environmental impact c per unit of semi-finished product i (t)	EISP _{i,c} (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	see sub-model environmental impacts	specific unit of c /m3 specific unit of c/kg	yes	yes	yes	no	no	within simulation	environmental impacts	wood value chain, socio-economics impacts
fair salary i	FS _i (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	FS _i (t) = ((SL _i / (WH _i (t)/ NE _i (t)) / MW))*100	dmnl	yes	no	no	no	yes	SLCA dataset	socio-economic impacts	no
minimum wage	MW	yes	auxiliary variable	CSR specific constant	€/h	yes	no	no	yes	no	literature	socio-economic impacts	no
Model: VALUE-ADDED													
wood price j,k (t)	WP _{j,k} (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	WP _{j,k} (t) = dataset (time series)	€/m3(f)	yes	no	yes	yes	no	data from WP1-4	value added	no
other raw material costs per unit i	ORMC _i	yes	auxiliary variable	constant, tbd	€/m3(f)	no	no	no	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	value added	no
wood quantity per unit i	WQ _i	yes	auxiliary variable	constant	m3(f)	no	no	no	no	no	literature	value added	no

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Model: VALUE-ADDED													
raw material costs per unit i,j,k (t)	$RMC_{i,j,k}(t)$	yes	auxiliary variable	$RMC(t) = WP_{j,k}(t) * WQ_i + ORMC_i * IR(t)$	€/m3(f)	yes	yes	yes	no	no	within simulation	value added	no
energy price (t)	EP (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	time dependent and CSR specific constant	€/kWh	yes	no	no	yes	no	input of future scenarios	value added	no
outbound logistic costs	OLC	yes	auxiliary variable	$OLC = FC * ATD$	€/m3(f)	yes	no	no	yes	no	within simulation	value added	no
other variable costs i	OVC_i	yes	auxiliary variable	constant	€/m3(f)	yes	no	yes	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	value added	no
salary per employee i	SLE_i	yes	auxiliary variable	constant	€/FTE	yes	yes	no	no	no	SLCA dataset	value added	wood value chain, socio-economics impacts
used energy per unit i	UE_i	yes	auxiliary variable	constant	kWh/m3(f)	no	no	yes	no	no	LCA dataset, literature	value added	environmental impacts
energy from raw material input per unit i	ERM_i	yes	auxiliary variable	constant ($WQ_i * SWEU_i * HV_j * BE_i$); external calculation	kWh/m3(f)	no	yes	yes	no	no	within simulation	value added	no
purchased energy per unit i	PE_i	yes	auxiliary variable	$PE_i = UE_i - ERM_i$	kWh/m3(f)	no	yes	yes	no	no	within simulation	value added	no
variable costs per unit i (t)	$VC_i(t)$	yes	auxiliary variable	$VC_i(t) = RMC_{i,j,k} + (EP(t) * PE) + (OVC_i + OLC - (BPP * PVBPI(t) / PVVC_i(t))) * IR(t)$	€/m3(f)	yes	yes	yes	no	no	within simulation	value added	no
calculatory fixed costs per year i	$CFCY_i$	yes	auxiliary variable	constant	€/m3(f)	no	yes	yes	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	value added	no
calculatory fixed costs per unit i (t)	$CFCU_i(t)$	yes	auxiliary variable	$CFCU_i(t) = (CFCY_i / PVVC_i(t)) * IR(t)$	€/m3(f)	yes	yes	yes	no	no	within simulation	value added	no
manufacturing costs per unit i (t)	$MC_i(t)$	yes	auxiliary variable	$MC_i(t) = VC_i(t) + CFCU_i(t)$	€/m3(f)	yes	yes	yes	no	no	within simulation	value added	no
administration and sales overhead rate i	ASO_i	yes	auxiliary variable	constant	€/m3(f)	yes	yes	no	no	no	statistical data of CSR	value added	no

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Model: VALUE-ADDED													
costs per unit i (t)	CU _i (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	$CU_{i(t)} = MC_i(t) + ASO_i *$ $MC_i(t)$	€/m3(f)	yes	yes	yes	no	no	within simulation	value added	no
profit margin per unit	PM	yes	auxiliary variable	constant	dmnl	no	yes	no	no	no	modelling an industrial sector	value added	no
total value added per unit i,j,k (t)	TVAU _{i,j,k} (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	$TVAU_{i,j,k}(t) = CU_i(t) + PM - RMC_{i,j,k}(t)$	€/m3(f)	yes	yes	yes	no	no	within simulation	value added	socio-economics impacts
wood fibre equivalent conversion factors i	WFE _i	yes	auxiliary variable	constant	dmnl	no	no	yes	no	no	literature	value added	no
production volume in value chain i (t)	PVVC _i (t)	yes	flow	see sub-model wood value chain	m3(f)/a	yes	yes	yes	no	no	MFA results per CSR	wood value chain	value added, environmental impacts, socio-economic impacts
production volume in value chain by-product i (t)	PVB _{Pi} (t)	yes	flow	see sub-model wood value chain	m3(f)/a	yes	yes	yes	no	no	MFA results per CSR	wood value chain	value added
total value added per wood fiber equivalent i,j,k (t)	TVAWF _{i,j,k} (t)	yes	stock	$TVAWF_{i,j,k}(t) = \text{Integral}(t=0 \text{ bis } t) (VAWF_{i,j,k}(t_0) + VAWF_{i,j,k}(t));$ $VAWF_{i,j,k}(t_0) = 0$	€	yes	yes	no	no	yes	within simulation	wood value chain	no
value added per wood fiber equivalent i,j,k per year (t)	VAWF _{i,j,k} (t)	no	flow	$VAWF_{i,j,k}(t) = TVAU_{i,j,k}(t) * WFE_i$	€/year	yes	yes	no	no	yes	within simulation	value added	no
by-product price i	BPP _i	yes	auxiliary variable	CSR specific constant	€/m3(f)	yes	no	no	no	no	statistical data of CSR	value added	no
value added per wood fiber equivalent by-product i,j,k (t)	VAWF _{Pi,j,k} (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	$VAWF_{Pi,j,k}(t) = BPP_i - (RMC_{i,j,k}(t) * WFE_i * RPBP_{i,j})$	€/m3(f)	yes	yes	no	no	no	within simulation	value added	no

SYSTEM ELEMENTS	abbreviation	included in the CLD	SFD type of element	equation	units	specific per CSR	specific for industry	specific for wood specie	exogenous factor	target indicator	input data	belongs to sub-model	interact with sub-model(s)
Model: VALUE-ADDED													
value added per wood fiber equivalent by-product i,j,k per year (t)	$VAWFBPY_{i,j,k}(t)$	no	flow	$VAWFBPY_i(t) = (BPP_i - (RMC_{i,j,k}(t) * WFE_i * RPBP_{i,j})) * PVBPI(t)$	€/year	yes	yes	no	no	no	within simulation	value added	no
total value added by-product i,j,k (t)	$TVABPY_{i,j,k}(t)$	no	stock	$TVABPY_{i,j,k}(t) = \text{Integral}(t=0 \text{ bis } t) (TVABPY_{i,j,k}(t_0) + VAWFBPY_{i,j,k}(t)) dt$ $TVABPY_{i,j,k}(t_0) = 0$	€	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	within simulation	value added	no
value added per wood fiber equivalent main product i,j,k (t)	$VAWFMP_{i,j,k}(t)$	yes	auxiliary variable	$VAWFMP_{i,j,k}(t) = VAWF_i(t) - VAWFBP_{i,j,k}(t)$	€/m3(f)	yes	yes	yes	no	no	within simulation	value added	no
value added main product per year i,j,k (t)	$VAMPY_{i,j,k}(t)$	no	flow	$VAMPY_{i,j,k}(t) = PVVC_i(t) * VAWFMP_{i,j,k}(t)$	€/year	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	within simulation	value added	no
total value added main product i,j,k (t)	$VAMP_{i,j,k}(t)$	no	stock	$VAMP_{i,j,k}(t) = \text{Integral}(t=0 \text{ bis } t) (VAMP_{i,j,k}(t_0) + VAMPY_{i,j,k}(t)) dt$ $VAMP_{i,j,k}(t_0) = 0$	€	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	within simulation	value added	no
average transport distance	ATD	no	auxiliary variable	CSR specific constant	km	yes	no	no	no	no	LCA assumption	value added	no
freight cost per km	FC	no	auxiliary variable	CSR specific constant	€/km	yes	no	no	no	no	statistical data of CSR	value added	no
inflation rate (t)	IR (t)	yes	auxiliary variable	$IR(t) = 1 + (IR(t_0) / 100) ^ t$; $IR(t_0) = \text{constant}$	dmnl	no	no	no	no	no	literature / assumption	value added	no
share of wood for energy use i	$SWEU_i$	no	auxiliary variable	constant	dmnl	no	yes	yes	no	no	literature	value added	no
heating value i	HV_i	no	auxiliary variable	constant	MJ/ kg	no	no	yes	no	no	literature	value added	no
burning efficiency i	BE_i	no	auxiliary variable	constant	dmnl	no	no	yes	no	no	literature	value added	no
relation main product to by-product i,j	$RPBP_{i,j}$	yes	auxiliary variable	see sub-model wood value chain	dmnl	yes	yes	yes	no	no	MFA results per CSR	wood value chain	value added

3.3.3 Example of a SFD in the sawmill industry

As an example for SD modelling the industrial value chain of sawmills is described (see Figure 13). It provides an example of the SFD, illustrating the inputs from other WPs, such as the forest growth model. It also includes external determinants derived from scenarios (based on the outcomes of Task 6.5 on future scenarios of the overriding FWVC), as well as target indicators that serve as the output of the simulation. A simulation per CSR will be done in Task 7.3 using the DVCVM as common background.

Figure 13. Example of SFD in a sawmill industry including input from other WPs (e.g., input from forest growth models), external determinants from scenarios and target indicators as outcome from the DVCVM simulation

4 Discussion, conclusions and outlook

4.1 Developing the DVCVM for scenario simulation

Systems approaches have gained extensive support for value chain management, with SD being applied specifically to primary industry value chains such as FWVC. Integrating the results from MFA, LCA and SLCA, the DVCVM address the linkages between wood supply, wood value-chain, environmental impacts, socio-economic impacts and value-added. Including not only input data from the forest growth, forest operations, wood assortments and quality forecast algorithm, but also the integrates the stakeholders expertise to develop and evaluate concepts for future scenarios of the FWVC.

The integrated approach of the SD with MFA, LCA and SLCA, improves analysis of strategies and policies. Specially because is including the analysis of an overview of the structure of wood flows from a retrospective point of view (MFA), the assessment of environmental and socio-economic impacts (LCA and SLCA), the future development of the FWVC, together with monetary evaluation of the value added model of the semi-finished wood products.

The simplification employed in developing the DVCM for the FWVC offers both advantages and potential disadvantages. The primary aim of simplification in the DVCM is to capture the essential features and dynamics of the FWVC. By simplifying the system elements and their relationships, the simulation of the DVCM will facilitate gaining insights, making predictions, and testing scenarios within a manageable and controllable framework. The abstraction and simplification enables the transferability to other CSRs by applying the modelling structure but adapting it to CSR-specific data for simulation. At all, the DVCM enables a better understanding of the complexities involved in the FWVC, exploration of potential outcomes, and informed decision-making processes.

However, it is important to acknowledge that these simplifications may lead to the loss of important details. Since a simplified model cannot fully capture all the intricacies and interactions present in real FWVCs, there is a possibility of overlooking crucial factors. It is necessary to strike a balance between simplicity and accuracy, ensuring that the simplified model remains representative enough to provide meaningful insights while considering the limitations of the simplification process.

In addition, utilizing a common DVCM across the CSRs in the FWVC offers several benefits. It improves efficiency by streamlining model development and data collection efforts. Comparisons between different CSRs become easier, facilitating standardized analysis and benchmarking. The model's scalability allows for adaptation to various regional characteristics while maintaining consistency in the modelling approach.

However, there are potential downsides to consider. A common DVCM may oversimplify the unique aspects of individual CSRs, leading to potential inaccuracies or limited understanding of specific regional contexts. Regional relevance and contextual factors might not be fully captured, limiting the model's applicability to address region-specific challenges or policy requirements. Variations in data availability and quality across CSRs can pose challenges, potentially affecting the reliability and accuracy of model outputs. Engaging stakeholders from the CSRs in the model's development and implementation is crucial to ensure ownership and applicability.

In summary, a common DVCM in the FWVC across different CSRs offers efficiency, comparability, transferability of insights, and scalability. However, it may oversimplify and overlook region-specific dynamics, face data challenges, and require active stakeholder engagement. Balancing standardization and customization is essential to maximize the model's effectiveness, relevance, and acceptance within the scientific report.

In the subsequent step, in Task 6.3, future scenarios are simulated in the DVCM to generate strategic options. Stakeholders' values are assessed through an analytical hierarchy process, validating the strategic options. The simulation results, along with stakeholder analysis and the value of forest ecosystem services, are analysed in a gap analysis to identify critical decision points. The revised strategic options are then integrated into the DVCM, enabling stakeholders to make informed decisions. These simulation-driven insights support policy-making and empower stakeholders to navigate the complex dynamics of the value chain.

4.2 Evaluation of the DVCM by the External Advisory Board

As milestone 12 within the project, the DVCM was presented to external advisory board (EAB). The EAB emphasizes the need for a comprehensive approach that is considering the forest management and wood value chain commonly and considering economic, ecological and social impacts. During presentation of the DVCM valuable feedback was provided by the (EAB) to enhance the DVCM in the FWVC. Various suggestions were discussed to improve the model's accuracy and relevance. One suggestion was to consider the inclusion of specific environmental impact categories, which are currently under consideration. The sensitivity of the model to data availability and contradictions was addressed, with an explanation of how the MFA methodology resolves data inconsistencies. The need to incorporate substitution effects and the exchange between different wood-based products into the model was emphasized, which was included in the environmental impacts sub-model.

The feedback received from the advisory board is instrumental in improving the DVCM. Their valuable input will contribute to refining and enhancing the model, ensuring its accuracy and relevance in capturing the dynamics of the FWVC. By considering the suggestions and recommendations provided, the DVCM will be better equipped to address key challenges and support informed decision-making processes.

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